

Inhibiting Factors of Health Services Puskesmas Auxiliary (Pustu) in Tobil Village, Togean District, Tojo Una-Una Regency

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study is to determine the inhibiting factors of health services of auxiliary health centers (pustu) in Tobil Village, Togean District, Tojo una-Una Regency. This research method is Descriptive qualitative. Location This research was conducted at the Tobil Village Sub-Health Center, Togean District, Tojo Una-una Regency. The results showed that the inhibiting factors of health services of the Auxiliary Health Center (pustu) in Tobil Village, Togean District, Tojo Una-una Regency. Which is seen from the factor of facilities hindering or inadequate and human resources (medical personnel) hindering because medical personnel are still lacking. This resulted in less than optimal health services provided by the auxiliary puskesmas (pustu) Tobil Village, Togean District, Tojo Una-una Regency. Auxiliary Puskesmas (pustu) In Tobil Village, Togean District, Tojo Una-una Regency, that there is still a lack of government budget for auxiliary puskesmas (pustu). So this is what hampers the health services of the auxiliary puskesmas (pustu) in Tobil Village.

INTRODUCTION

Puskesmas Auxiliary (pustu), which has an important role in ensuring the community gets the best service, is also an important public institution in people's lives. Auxiliary health centers are one of the health facilities that are in great demand or used by the community, so strengthening the health service system is important. The maintenance of patient health in an area is also greatly helped by the existence of auxiliary health facilities (pustu). The need for good and quality health services provided by health care providers in order to achieve the highest degree of public health in health efforts, as stated in the Regulation of the Minister of Health of the Republic of Indonesia Number 75 of 2014 concerning community health centers (puskesmas).

To achieve a high degree of public health in the region, supporting puskesmas must prioritize mutual assistance to puskesmas in promotive and preventive efforts. However, there are still often weaknesses in some auxiliary Puskesmas (pustu) regarding health services that are still unsatisfactory. As happened at the Auxiliary Puskesmas (pustu) in Tobil Village, Togeang District, Tojo Una-Una Regency. There are still some things that make the community still feel dissatisfied with the services of the Auxiliary Puskesmas (pustu), as researchers found in the auxiliary puskesmas (pustu) in Tobil Village, Togeang District, Tojo Una-Una Regency, namely, there is still a lack of health support. Based on the standards that have been set, the auxiliary Puskesmas (pustu) should already have health support that is able to provide the best service for the community. But the auxiliary health center (pustu) in Tobil Village is still inadequate. As well as the lack of competence of health workers, in the auxiliary Puskesmas (pustu) should be assisted by several nurses and midwives, but in fact in the auxiliary Puskesmas (pustu) Tobil Village there is only 1 Midwife, while the population of Tobil Village, Togeang District, Tojo Una-Una Regency is divided into 4 Hamlets whose population is 879 people. Therefore, it is very ineffective if there is only 1 midwife in the Auxiliary Health Center (pustu) of Tobil Village, Togeang District, Tojo Una-una Regency. Then regarding the maintenance of the puskesmas, it is known that a community health unit or auxiliary puskesmas (pustu) must maintain the condition of the puskesmas so that people who come for treatment will feel comfortable with its services. However, the auxiliary puskesmas (pustu) in Tobil Village is not well maintained. We need to know that the health service system also greatly impacts the willingness of the community to visit the service place or puskesmas. Therefore, the researchers conducting this study were to determine the inhibiting factors of health services of auxiliary health centers (pustu) in Tobil Village, Togeang District, Tojo una-Una Regency.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Service Concept

Service is a need that must be maximized and is one of the spearheads that is very important for the success of various businesses or efforts to fulfill service activities. Because the quality of the person or organization that provides services is reflected in the form of service, the service will play a greater and more important role in community activities. Menurut

(Hardiyansyah, 2022). The service process covers the entire life of the organization in society because service is basically a series of actions that occur regularly and continuously.

Service

The most important aspect in health services is the happiness of the environment around the health facility. To develop and maintain high-quality healthcare services in response to international competition, the main principle of the organization is public satisfaction with health services. So that we can improve technology and human resources while producing high-quality services. 2019 (Imran & Ramli). Comparing the performance of healthcare professionals within an organization with expectations that align with their level of trust will result in satisfaction for those seeking services. Because of the marketing stimulus, if the patient feels satisfied it will greatly affect his experience of undergoing further therapy. (Riadi, 2016). People who use health services can be considered satisfied if they do so, and dissatisfaction is a problem that needs to be addressed immediately in order to maintain and improve the quality of health services. (Pasalli & Patattan, 2021)

Quality of Service

Service quality is described as the desired level of perfection and control over that level of excellence to satisfy customer needs (Chandra & Tjiptono, 2016). The point of view of the provider or service provider on the quality of service is not considered. Customers must evaluate and decide on the level of service because they are the ones who use and feel the goods and services offered.

Human Resource Management (HRM)

Sumarsono (2017) stated that the term "human resources" has two meanings. The first is the potential for commercial employment or services throughout production. Human resource management (HRM) in Hasibuan (2022) can be interpreted as the science and art of controlling the interaction and work functions of the workforce to ensure effective and efficient in achieving business, labor, and community goals.

Manus Resource Management Functionia

According to Hasibuan (2016: 20-23) Human resource management functions include: Planning, organizing, directing, managing, procurement, development, dismissal, compensation, maintenance, punishment, and dismissal are just some of the tasks involved in human resource management. The term "health care quality assurance" refers to a broad initiative aimed at offering medical services of the highest caliber, that is, medical services that comply with established medical service standards. Health care that consistently exceeds patient expectations is considered to be of high quality. Quality healthcare organizations attract healthcare professionals as well as patients, making them a desirable place for competent and ethical healthcare

professionals to work. Based on the description of the objectives above, the following research mindset was compiled:

Figure 1. Research Mindset

METHODOLOGY

The research method used is qualitative descriptive research. The location of this research is centered in the Tobil Village Health Center, Togeian District, Tojo Una-Una Regency, with reasons as a source of data in this study consisting of primary data and secondary data. Data collection techniques through observation, structured interviews, and documentation. This data analysis is carried out inductively based on empirical evidence including: Data Reduction, Data Presentation, and conclusions or verification.

RESULTS

Human Resources (Medical Personnel)

The resources referred to in this study are those related to medical officers whether they have provided good services in supporting the process of health services for the community. Key Informant (ID) who served as director of Puskesmas was interviewed and obtained the following findings:

"In my opinion, human resources (medical personnel) play an important role in the process of providing health services to patients at Puskesmas Auxiliary (pustu) in Tobil Village, Togeian District, and Tojo Una-una Regency, and I, as the leader of the Puskesmas, always receive complaints from the local community regarding the need for medical personnel, supporting facilities, and infrastructure that is still substandard. I will also try to improve the services provided by the auxiliary health center (pus It will take the time to correct these shortcomings, so I hope the community can be patient (conversation on June 19, 2023).

From the informant's statement above, it can be concluded that the infrastructure and supporting facilities of the Puskesmas (pustu) are still below standard and the supporting human resources of the Puskesmas (pustu) are still lacking. In this case, it is considered bad because it can interfere with the

services received by patients who seek treatment at the sub-district health center (pustu) in Tobil Village, Togeang District, or Tojo Una-una Regency. The results of interviews with informants (NM) as Midwives said that:

"As a medical officer, of course, I always provide the best service to patients who come for treatment, but this puskesmas still lacks medical personnel so it is an obstacle for us," (conversation June 19, 2023)

From the informant's narrative above, the author can conclude that medical personnel are needed to handle patients, but the scarcity of medical personnel hampers the implementation of health services at the District Health Center (pustu). The results of interviews with informants (ZP) as village heads stated that:

"I think the performance of human resources (medical personnel) in the auxiliary puskesmas (pustu) is quite good, but we here experience some difficulties in finding human resources (medical personnel) because of limited human resources. But we will try our best to get medical personnel" (interview on June 26)

From the informant's statement above, it can be concluded that there is a need for additional medical personnel at the auxiliary puskesmas (pustu). The results of interviews with informants (SN) as people (patients) who have come for treatment at auxiliary health centers (pustu) stated that:

"The service is already quite good, but there I think there is still a lack of medical personnel because I was there waiting a long time to get service". (interview on July 10)

From the informant's statement above, it can be concluded that human resources (medical personnel) in auxiliary puskesmas (pustu) need to be added so that services can run smoothly. The results of interviews from informant informants (BLK) as the patient's family stated that:

"I once took my mother for treatment at the Puskesmas Auxiliary (Pustu) to go check the pain she complained about, and there I saw only 1 medical officer, and I felt bored waiting for the medical officer to serve my mother, but I hope to understand because maybe the medical officer there is still lacking". (interview on July 10)

From the results of the overall interview above, it shows that human resources (medical personnel) are still lacking in number, namely only 1 Midwife. While people who come for treatment are sometimes more than 2 or 3 people, this is what hampers health services at the auxiliary puskesmas (pustu) in Tobil Village, Togeang District, Tojo Una-una Regency.

Facilities

The facilities referred to in this study are the availability of medical facilities to support health services at the auxiliary puskesmas (pustu) of Tobil Village. The results of interviews with informants (ID) of the head of the puskesmas said that:

"In providing health services at the auxiliary Puskesmas (pustu) it is in accordance with existing procedures, however, the obstacles are the condition of the building, small or narrow rooms and the existing facilities are only sober, so

it is difficult to provide health services to patients, but in that case we still try to provide services as much as possible that can satisfy the community." (interview June 19).

From the informant's statement above, it can be concluded that in providing health services to patients, it is also necessary to pay attention to the facilities, because this can also hamper health services for patients who need services. The results of interviews with informants (NM) as Midwives said that:

"In my opinion, the completeness of the facilities in the auxiliary puskesmas (pustu) can be said to be inadequate, there is a need for additional facilities such as delivery rooms and examination rooms where we all know that delivery rooms and examinations are very important and it can be one of the inhibiting factors for individual and community health services, so if I think this can be one of the inhibiting factors health services" (interview June 19, 2023)

From the informant's statement above that the author can conclude that the facilities in the auxiliary puskesmas (pustu) are still fairly inadequate because there are not yet several rooms, so it is expected that the district / city government will anticipate this. The results of interviews with informants (SN) as people who have come for treatment to the auxiliary puskesmas (pustu) said that:

"In my opinion, the facilities in the auxiliary puskesmas (pustu) are still incomplete, there are some facilities that are not yet owned by the auxiliary puskesmas (pustu) of Tobil Village which should already be owned by a auxiliary puskesmas (pustu) in general, especially the room for childbirth". (interview July 10, 2023).

From the informant's statement above, the author can conclude that the facilities in the auxiliary puskesmas (pustu) of tobil village need to be added, because to maintain the possibility that there are people who come to give birth but do not have a room for childbirth, while we know that it is very important for an auxiliary puskesmas (pustu). The results of interviews from informant informants (BLK) as the patient's family stated that:

"Inmy opinion, the facilities at the auxiliary health center (pustu) are still fairly inadequate, because the seats provided are very limited, the waiting room is narrow" (interview on July 10, 2023)

From the informant's statement above, the researcher concluded that the services provided by the auxiliary puskesmas (pustu) are still not optimal, it is necessary to add seats for patients and patients' families. From the results of the overall interview above, it shows that the facilities in the auxiliary puskesmas (pustu) are still very inadequate because there is no delivery room, examination room, beds and seats provided are still lacking, this results in less than optimal health services in the auxiliary puskesmas (pustu) Tobil Village.

Government Attention

The government's attention referred to in this study is a role of the local government in an auxiliary puskesmas (pustu) regarding the maintenance of the puskesmas, policies and government support for the auxiliary puskesmas (pustu). The results of interviews with informants (ID) of the head of the puskesmas said that:

"In my opinion, the village government's support for the auxiliary puskesmas (pustu) already exists but is not fulfilled all only partially, because many are funded in the village". interview June 19).

From the informant's statement above, researchers can conclude that village government participation regarding puskesmas auxiliary (pustu) exists but is not fulfilled all because of insufficient funds. The results of interviews with informants (NM) as Midwives said that:

"In my opinion, government support regarding the maintenance or support of auxiliary puskesmas (pustu) activities has been submitted, but not all of them are acc, only a few are borne by the village government due to insufficient funds," (interview June 19).

From the informant's statement above, researchers can conclude that government support for puskesmas auxiliary (pustu) is only partially borne by the village government. The results of the interview with the informant (ZP) as the head of Tobil village stated that:

"In my opinion, regarding the auxiliary puskesmas (pustu) as a whole, it is not a fix from the village, there are some related agencies but so far what we can help is only to fund the consumption problems of toddlers, the elderly, stunting, only about such funds, if technically it is about the maintenance of the auxiliary puskesmas building (pustu) not from the village government but from the related agency". (interview on June 26)

From the informant's statement above, the researcher concluded that the government has provided support for the auxiliary puskesmas (pustu), it's just that not all can be covered by the village government, especially regarding the maintenance of the auxiliary puskesmas (pustu) that is part of the related agency. The results of interviews with informants (SN) as people who have come for treatment to the auxiliary puskesmas (pustu) said that:

"In my opinion, the government's attention regarding the auxiliary puskesmas (pustu) exists, but it is still not fully considered, especially about the maintenance of the auxiliary puskesmas (pustu). Especially regarding the building that needs to be rehapped so that it still looks suitable for use".

From the informant's statement above, the researcher concluded that government attention is needed again in order to devour the auxiliary puskesmas building (pustu) in order to make people come for treatment comfortably. The results of interviews from informants (BLK) as the patient's family stated that:

"In my opinion, the auxiliary puskesmas (pustu) has not fully received the government's attention because it can be seen from the auxiliary puskesmas (pustu) building which still has many shortcomings, not like the auxiliary puskesmas (pustu) in general, which is clean and comfortable".

From the informant's statement above, the researcher concluded that there is a need for comfort for people who come for treatment to the auxiliary puskesmas (pustu), this is if the auxiliary puskesmas (pustu) is well maintained, for the government needs to pay more attention to the auxiliary puskesmas (pustu) in Tobil Village.

DISCUSSION

The discussion of the findings of this study can be concluded from the description of the results of the interview and analysis above that human resources (medical personnel), facilities, and attention are the main factors inhibiting the implementation of health services in supporting health centers. (pustu) in Tobil Village, Togeian District, and Tojo Una Regency. governments that interfere with or oppose health care.

The survival of a corporate organization (private sector) or government bureaucratic organization depends almost entirely on the quality of its services. In an effort to achieve public service user happiness (customer satisfaction), providing good service and meeting user demands is very important. All operations must be based on the wishes and preferences of service users if a company wants to become a customer-oriented enterprise, as failure to accurately identify these needs and expectations will result in meaningless and ineffective service provision. Governments can contribute to the expansion or improvement of health services in several ways, including through improved systems and information flows that enable policymakers to identify trends in public health issues.

In this study, the state of human resources (medical personnel) became the main topic of discussion. Whether the supporting puskesmas (pustu) provides comfort to patients or not, this activity is related to the work offered by the pustu. Research findings show that the inhibiting factor of health services in the sub-district health centers (pustu) in Tobil Village, Togeian District, and Tojo Una-una Regency is a human resource factor (medical personnel) that hinders because there is only one midwife and insufficient medical personnel. Auxiliary health facilities (pustu) in Tobil Village, Togeian District, and Tojo Una-una Regency provide less than ideal health services.

Accessibility to facilities provided by Puskesmas in providing services to the community is a component of facilities in this study. The research findings show the obstacles faced by the sub-district health centers (pustu) in Tobil Village, Togeian District, and Tojo Una-una Regency in providing health services. Its consideration indicates that the facilities are limited or insufficient. This is due to a lack of delivery rooms, examination rooms, beds, and other equipment in facilities owned by sponsored public health clinics. The service is subpar because of this.

In terms of government policy considerations, government policy towards auxiliary puskesmas (pustu) is being discussed. The results of this study show that there are several factors that contribute to the failure of auxiliary puskesmas (pustu) services in Tobil Village, Togeian District, and Tojo Una-una. Therefore, this situation weakens the health services provided to auxiliary puskesmas (pustu) in the transportation area.

The government's attention is still focused on the study of inhibiting factors for health services in puskesmas kecamatan (pustu) in Tobil Village, Togeian District, and Tojo Una-una Regency in terms of Human Resources Factors (medical personnel). . This lack of support hinders Puskesmas

Assistants (pustu) in Tobil Village, Togean District, and Tojo Una-una Regency from providing health services.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Factors Inhibiting Health Services at the Sub-Pustu (Pustu) are seen from Human Resources (medical personnel), Facilities Factors and Government attention factors that hinder or do not support enough, for the Health Services at the Sub-Pustu (Pustu) in Tobil Village, Togean District, Tojo Regency, Una-una. Therefore, it is necessary to add facilities in the form of a delivery room, examination room, bed and seating. This needs to be anticipated in order to optimize health services at the sub-district health center (pustu) in Tobil Village, Togean District. b). There is a need for the Tojo Una-una Regency health service to pay more attention to the sub-district health centers (pustu) so that sub-district health centers (pustu) health services are more effective and meet expectations. c). There is a need for coordination between the community health center and the district/city government regarding existing problems at the community health center, such as additional human resources (medical personnel), additional facilities and government attention regarding the building of supporting community health centers (pustu) so that health services can run smoothly.

FURTHER STUDY

In this study, the researcher only studied the factors inhibiting health services at the supporting public health center (pustu) in Tobil Village, Togean District, Tojo una-Una Regency, including: human resource factors, facilities and government attention, and did not examine other supporting factors in determining success. health services. Therefore, researchers can further expand the scope of their scientific studies to make them more complex.

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